

Whole-genome synteny-based phylogeny of apes supports the pongid clade, excluding humans

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Key words: synteny, genetic equidistance, molecular clock, neutral theory, maximum genetic diversity theory, apes, hominids, hominoids, pongid

Abstract

Molecular phylogenetic studies utilize protein and DNA sequences to infer phylogeny. The first set of protein alignment results in the 1960s uncovered a most astonishing phenomenon, the genetic equidistance, which directly inspired the molecular clock hypothesis and in turn the neutral theory of molecular evolution. One of the earlier results of molecular phylogeny based on the molecular clock perspective is on the hominids, which surprisingly grouped chimpanzees with humans rather than other great apes, in contrast to the anatomy-based phylogeny popular before the molecular era that groups the great apes into the pongid clade with human as the outgroup. However, recent developments have deemed the molecular clock and the neutral theory flawed in their core claims. The genetic equidistance phenomenon has been reinterpreted by a new evolutionary perspective, the maximum genetic diversity theory. It is now realized that genetic distances are mostly at maximum saturation rather than still scaling with time as misread by the molecular clock. One must choose the few slowly evolving genes that have yet to reach maximum genetic distance to perform phylogenetic inferences. We have previously used the so-called slow clock method to rewrite the hominid phylogeny, which has confirmed the anatomy-based model. Synteny, the conserved collinearity of orthologous genetic loci in two or more organisms, exhibits compelling phylogenomic potential. Using synteny revealed by whole-genome assembly-assembly alignments, we here tested the two competing models of hominid phylogeny and found strong support for the pongid clade through synteny analysis. We provide a first-principle rationale for the pongid clade and review the extensive body of studies that support the pongid clade.

Introduction

The field of molecular evolution and molecular phylogeny got started in the 1960s by an astonishing set of protein alignment results that includes the genetic equidistance result [1, 2]. Different ingroup sister species are approximately equidistant to a simpler reference outgroup species [1]. This phenomenon was unexpected from the Darwinian theory of natural selection and explained by proposing an ad hoc hypothesis, the molecular clock, claiming that all species have similar mutation rates [3]. The molecular clock was regarded as a true reality by some researchers, which then inspired the neutral theory of molecular evolution [4]. The molecular clock and the neutral theory have served as the foundation for the new field of molecular phylogeny [3]. The basic idea is that phylogenetic distance scales with time.

Prior to the molecular era, the consensus view on the phylogeny of hominids was that human is the outgroup to a pongid (orangutan-gorilla-chimpanzees) clade and diverged from pongids ~18 million years ago (mya) [5-7]. It is an anatomy-based model (Figure 1A). In contrast, popular interpretations of molecular data suggest that humans and chimpanzees belong to the same clade to the exclusion of other great apes and shared a common ancestor merely 5 mya [8], which led to a molecular tree of hominids very different from the anatomy-based tree (Figure 1B). More recently, forced by new fossil findings such as the 6-7 million year old *Orrorin tugenensis* and *Sahelanthropus tchadensis*, the human-chimpanzee split time has been modified to be at 7 mya [9, 10].

However, it has been realized in recent years that the interpretation of the genetic equidistance phenomenon by the molecular clock and neutral theory is actually mistaken. A new and more correct molecular evolutionary theory has been proposed, termed the maximum genetic diversity (MGD) theory [11]. Genetic distances are mostly at maximum or optimum saturation rather than still scaling with time as misread by the molecular clock. The maximum genetic diversity theory explains the genetic equidistance phenomenon as a result of maximum genetic distance [12-14]. Over a long evolutionary time and for fast-evolving DNAs, the genetic distance between species has reached the maximum

level. The distance between the ingroup species and a simpler outgroup taxon is mainly determined by the maximum genetic diversity of the simpler outgroup. This distance is equal to the maximum distance allowed within members of the simpler outgroup, e.g., the distance between humans and fishes equals the maximum distance between different taxa of fishes. Changes in the lineage leading to the simpler outgroup mask any changes in the lineages leading to the ingroup taxa.

One of the ways to test the molecular clock versus the maximum genetic diversity theory is the genetic non-equidistance result despite equidistance in time [15]. The maximum genetic diversity theory predicts that equidistance would only result when the outgroup is less complex than the sister species. If the outgroup is more complex, then its maximum distance with the ingroup sister species would be determined by the MGD of each of the ingroup species, which may not be the same for all the ingroup species. However, the molecular clock would predict genetic equidistance to the outgroup regardless if the outgroup taxon is more or less complex. For example, human is the outgroup to the Sauropsida clade containing snake and bird. The molecular clock predicts that humans should be equidistant to snakes and birds in protein sequence. However, the maximum genetic diversity theory predicts that birds should be closer to humans than snakes should because birds should be more complex than snakes. The actual data in fact validated the maximum genetic diversity theory [12, 15, 16].

Genetic non-equidistance to humans despite equidistance in time has also been found for sister species within the teleost fish clade, the arthropod phylum, the Porifera phylum, and the fungi kingdom [15]. In all cases where the difference in complexity of the ingroup sister species can be inferred (octopus vs. cockle, terebratulina vs. lingula, bird vs. snake, dragonfly vs. louse, and smut vs. yeast), the more complex species always shows greater sequence similarity to humans in fast-evolving genes, fully conforming to the predictions of the maximum genetic diversity theory but not that of the molecular clock. Also, by whole genome sequencing analysis, two New World monkeys are found to be non-equidistant in nucleotide sequence to humans with the most primitive monkey marmoset to be more distant to humans than the owl monkey [17].

The maximum genetic diversity theory has direct impact on phylogenetic methods. Past methods have no concept of maximum distance and use mostly non-informative data for inferring phylogeny. They often produce self-conflicting results and results inconsistent with the fossil records and morphology [18]. We developed the slow clock method based on the maximum genetic diversity theory [15]. The method utilizes only slow evolving sequences, which ensures the linear relationship between distance and time. Its results therefore will be more objective and independent of the variations in sequence selections. In keeping with the intuitive logic, important genes mutate less often [19]. Slowly evolving sequences are more likely to meet the neutral criteria and in fact are indeed more neutral [20]. Truly neutral sequences still at the linear phase of divergence, many of the assumptions of the neutral theory would be valid. Thus phylogenetics research can largely proceed as before except that one has now a standard to separate the neutral from the noninformative DNAs. One must now distinguish two different kinds of high sequence similarity, one due to less time of separation and the other because of common construction resulting in using similar parts (convergent evolution).

We have used the slow clock method to vindicate the anatomy-based hominid phylogeny that humans and pongids are two separate groups [15]. Chimpanzees have more reasoning ability than orangutans [21]. Therefore, that chimpanzees are more similar to humans in DNA than other great apes in the pongid clade is actually a typical case of the above mentioned genetic non-equidistance despite equidistance in time.

Synteny—the conservation of local gene content and order at the nuclear chromosome level—has been recently recognized as a valuable source of phylogenetic information [22, 23]. Closely related species are expected to share a high degree of synteny. While it has long been known that the great apes of the pongid clade share the same number of chromosomes—two more than humans—it remains unknown whether, aside from having the same number of chromosomes, there is a higher degree of synteny among the great apes compared to the synteny between great apes and humans. The pongid clade could be either verified or falsified by studying the synteny among the hominids.

The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) has recently launched a new visualization tool for analysis of whole-genome assembly-assembly alignments, the Comparative Genome Viewer (CGV) [24]. CGV visualizes pairwise same-species and cross-species alignments, revealing synteny information in visually clear plots. We here utilized these synteny plots to test the two competing models of hominid phylogeny or to investigate whether the pongid clade is better supported by synteny than the alternative model.

Results:

The plots of whole-genome assembly-assembly alignments among the apes or hominoids were performed by the CGV team and captured as screenshots from the CGV website (Figure 2). We visually inspected the degree of synteny for each pair of species within the apes. A higher degree of synteny is inferred when there are fewer reverse alignments, when a chromosome is not aligned to multiple chromosomes, or when there are more forward alignments. As a positive control, we first checked whether the two closely related great ape species, *Pan troglodytes* and *Pan paniscus*, shared a higher degree of synteny than chimpanzee and gorilla (CC vs. CG). Among all 24 pairs of chromosomes, 20 showed a higher degree of synteny and 3 showed a lower degree for CC compared to CG (Table 1 and Figure 3). We defined a synteny ratio in an AB vs. BC or AB vs. CD comparison as BC/AB or CD/AB , i.e., the number of chromosomes with higher synteny for BC or CD divided by the number of chromosomes with higher synteny for AB. A smaller ratio (<1) indicates greater degree of synteny for AB relative to BC or CD. Therefore, for CC vs. CG, the synteny ratio is $CG/CC = 3/20 = 0.15$, confirming the expected result that the degree of synteny between the two chimpanzee species is greater than that between chimpanzees and gorillas. We further found as expected that two different species of the orangutan clade, *Pongo abelii* and *Pongo pygmaeus*, showed higher degree of synteny compared to between gorillas and orangutans (OO vs. GO, synteny ratio 0.10).

We next examined whether chimpanzees and gorillas are closer to each other in synteny than either is to humans. As shown in Table 1 and Figure 3, chimpanzees and gorillas showed higher degree of synteny than chimpanzees and orangutans (CG vs. CO, synteny ratio 0.50), gorilla and orangutans (CG vs. GO, synteny ratio 0.44), humans and orangutans (CG vs. HO, synteny ratio 0.45), or chimpanzees and humans (CG vs. CH, synteny ratio 0.75). We further examined whether chimpanzees and humans show a lower degree of synteny compared to chimpanzees and orangutans, gorillas and orangutans, or humans and orangutans. The results indicated that chimpanzees and humans showed a similar degree of synteny to that of CO, GO, or HO (synteny ratios 0.75 to 1 for CH vs. CO, vs. GO, or vs. HO), which did not indicate a substantially smaller synteny ratio (<0.5) comparable to or smaller than what was found for the chimpanzee-gorilla clade. The results strongly support the anatomy-based or the slow-clock-based phylogeny that chimpanzees and gorillas belong to the same African apes clade to the exclusion of humans, and invalidate the alternative model that chimpanzees and humans belong to the same clade to the exclusion of gorillas.

If the popular phylogeny is correct that gorilla is the outgroup to a supposed chimpanzee-human clade, the degree of synteny between gorilla and human should be similar to that between gorilla and chimpanzee and higher than that between human and orangutan or between gorilla and orangutan. However, the synteny ratio for CG vs. HG is 0.17, supporting the chimpanzee-gorilla clade. The synteny ratio for HG vs. GO and HG vs. HO were 1.6 and 1.2, respectively, indicating that humans and gorillas share a lower degree of synteny than gorillas and orangutans or humans and orangutans. The result of synteny ratios here also implied a higher degree of synteny for gorillas and orangutans than for humans and orangutans, which is fully expected if the pongid clade is true. Thus, the popular notion of a chimpanzee-human clade was not supported by synteny.

If the pongid clade with human as the outgroup is true, the human-orangutan relationship as informed by synteny should be more distant than the chimpanzee-orangutan relationship or the gorilla-orangutan relationship. Indeed, the synteny ratios for CO vs. HO or GO vs. HO were all smaller than 1,

indicating that orangutans are closer to the African apes than to humans, consistent with the pongid clade or the result of the slow clock method that African apes are closer to orangutans than humans are in slowly evolving genes [15].

If the hominid clade with gibbon as the outgroup is real, the human-gibbon relationship should be more distant than the human-orangutan relationship. Results showed that the synteny ratio for HO vs. HGi is much smaller than 1, confirming gibbons as the outgroup to the hominid clade.

Discussions:

Our study revealed extensive degree of synteny among the great apes of the pongid clade, which is not necessarily obvious or expected based solely on the well-known sharing of the same number of chromosomes among these great apes. The results are also not expected from the popular molecular model of the hominid phylogeny but are fully consistent with the phylogeny based on anatomy and the slow clock method [15]. The African apes clade excluding humans, the pongid clade excluding humans, and the hominid clade excluding gibbons are all well supported by synteny as found here. We also made sure that synteny as detected by our method here is well informative to hominid phylogeny by showing that closely related hominids such as between two different species of chimpanzees or two different species of orangutans showed the expected high degree of synteny. In addition, the expected high degree of synteny between human and orangutan relative to human and gibbon was also shown by our method.

That chimpanzees and gorillas share a higher degree of synteny than chimpanzees and humans as revealed here is striking and would have to be due to convergent evolution or specially fast changes in chromosomal structure in the human branch if the popular phylogeny is real. On the other hand, the higher similarity in genome sequence between chimpanzees and humans would have to be due to convergent evolution if the anatomy- or the slow-clock-based phylogeny is true. However, the

molecular grouping of chimpanzees with humans has now a good explanation in the maximum genetic diversity theory as nothing more than the common phenomenon of genetic non-equidistance despite equidistance in time, which shows that convergent evolution at nucleotide sequence level is very common [15]. If one wouldn't group a particular monkey (owl monkey) with humans to the exclusion of another monkey (marmoset) in the New World monkey clade simply because the former is closer to humans than the latter in whole genome DNA sequence [17], one would have little justification for doing so for one great ape relative to another within the pongid clade.

One way to easily determine if one is dealing with a genetic non-equidistance phenomenon is to see whether the extra distance to the outgroup C in DNA for species B relative to its ingroup sister species A is much smaller than the distance between B and C or A and C. The extra distance of gorillas to humans relative to chimpanzees is 0.36%, much smaller than the distance of gorillas to humans ~1.62% or the distance of chimpanzees to humans ~1.26% [17]. The extra distance of marmoset to humans is 0.5% relative to owl monkey, much smaller than the distance of marmoset to humans ~9.7% or the distance of owl monkey to humans ~9.2% [17]. Suppose the distance of chimpanzees to humans is 0.6%, the extra distance of gorillas to humans relative to chimpanzees would be 1.02%, which would be greater than the distance of chimpanzees to humans. In such an imagined case, it would be correct to group chimpanzees with humans rather than with gorillas. Such a significant difference between the two great apes in their DNA distances to humans would imply that chimpanzees would share much more trait similarities with humans than they are with gorillas, as DNA similarity should be a good although not perfect indication of trait similarity.

Given highly similar genome sequences, dramatic difference in traits is not uncommon, which can be accomplished by utilizing very different architectural maps or epigenetic programs that determine how DNA genes are utilized or expressed. Epigenetic programs are determined in a large part by chromatin structures and chemical modifications of histones and DNA [25]. A higher degree of synteny indicates a higher degree of similarity in epigenetic programs. Convergent evolution in

epigenetic programs is relatively rare or has yet to be reported. Chimpanzees are closer to humans in genome sequences but to gorillas in both synteny and traits, clearly indicating a more important role of epigenetic programs in shaping traits, or in chimpanzees being closer to gorillas in most traits than to humans.

If the pongid clade and the human branch have parted ways 18 mya as shown by the slow clock method as well as by the consensus view based on the fossil record prior to the molecular era [15], it is likely that the synteny divergence of humans and great apes also started then. An earlier divergence of humans and great apes makes more sense based on first-principles than a later divergence following further differentiation along the great apes lineage. The most recent common ancestor of humans and great apes must have been more stem-like or undifferentiated, with more commonalities shared among humans and great apes and fewer specialized features of either humans or great apes. An earlier human divergence means that the first branching differentiation of the descendants of the great ape-human common ancestor would have already separated the human branch from the great apes branch (Figure 1A). But if the human divergence occurred much later as postulated by the popular model (7 mya), the first branching differentiation of the hominids would separate the orangutan branch from the African great apes branch (including humans) (Figure 1B). Both branches include great apes, and so both represent a further specialization and differentiation along the great apes lineage. The specialization and further differentiation toward more great-apes-like (such as knuckle walking) would not be conducive to the transformation from great apes to humans. As shown by the law of irreversibility of evolution (Dollo's Law), a trait usually cannot lose its differentiation and return to a less derived or stem state [26]. In addition, the popular model suggests that the African great apes branch later divided into two branches: the gorilla branch and the chimpanzee branch (including humans) (Figure 1B), both of which also include great apes, which therefore represents another further specialization and differentiation along the great ape lineage rather than the human lineage. This would only further increase the difficulty in transforming great apes to humans. Therefore, the pongid clade is

more reasonable based on first principles. Humans were separated before any further specialization and differentiation of great apes, and underwent major changes in synteny as revealed here. The earlier divergence also gave humans more time to specialize and evolve.

Consistent with the synteny conservation within the pongid clade observed here, there are only 2 shared inversions for the bonobo-chimpanzee-human grouping, which is in contrast to the real grouping of the bonobo-chimpanzee-gorilla clade with 13 shared inversions and the pongid clade with 31 shared inversions [27].

Supporting our results, a Miocene ape fossil of 11.6 million years ago in Europe, *Danuvius guggenmosi*, showed bipedal features, consistent with a separation of the human lineage from the great apes earlier than 12 million years ago [28]. The recently published *Lufengpithecus* fossil of 8 mya has thick enamels and bipedal features, indicating that it may be a close sister lineage to the human branch [29]. Bipedal features inferred from foot and hand anatomy have been proposed to be present in the most recent common ancestor of hominids [30]. Analysis of foot bones supports the pongid clade [31]. There are also findings indicating the early occurrence at 12.5 mya of chimpanzee- and gorilla-like fossils, being several million years earlier than the popular dating results [32]. Such earlier appearance of bipedal features and chimpanzee-like fossils cannot be easily reconciled with the original molecular dating of human-chimpanzee separation at 5 mya. It could only be done by fudging the parameters of the molecular clock method, which would represent meaningless pseudoscientific gameplay.

There are a number of different fossil apes around 17-15 mya in Africa that can be divided roughly into two major groups [33]. Group one has no suspension adaptation in locomotion and may have migrated to Eurasia around 15-14 mya and given rise to the lineage that may have evolved into *Danuvius* and *Lufengpithecus*. Some species of this lineage may have moved back to Africa around 6-8 mya due to climate change to a desertic one in Western Asia [34]. Group two also may have moved to Eurasia around 16-14 Myr ago [35]. Change to temperate climate in late Miocene in Eurasia may have

caused some descendant species of this group to move back to Africa leading to African apes and some to tropical South East Asia leading to orangutans.

Also, new findings push back the oldest evidence of C4 grass-dominated habitats in Africa—and globally—by more than 10 million years to 17-21 million years ago [36]. Such habitats are believed by the popular Savanna theory to have favored an upright posture and selected for bipedalism. A large increase in grassland is known to be associated with the extinction of certain great apes in China such as the giant ape *Gigantopithecus blacki* [37]. Thus, the newly corrected dating for C4 grass appearance in Africa fully supports the pongid clade and invalidates the popular human-chimpanzee clade.

There are additional many lines of evidence supporting the pongid clade, which include the conservation in anatomy and behavior [7, 38], human heart left ventricle being diverged away from a more trabeculated phenotype present in all other great apes [39], chimpanzee neurons having gene expression profiles that are more similar to those of gorilla neurons than to those of human neurons [40, 41], certain cis-regulatory-element-frequencies related gene expression controls being reorganized along the human lineage while conserved in chimpanzees and orangutans [42], the lineage-specific expansions of retroviral insertions within the genomes of African great apes but not humans and orangutans [43]; a chimpanzee-gorilla orthologous PtERV1 element that is not present in humans [44]; the incongruence for 35.8% of the human genome with the popular phylogenetic tree for the African apes, which has been explained away by the unprovable notion of incomplete lineage sorting but is more likely the result of convergent evolution [44]; the gorilla and chimpanzee genomes sharing a number of structural mutation that have not occurred in humans, including the formation of subtelomeric heterochromatic caps, the hyperexpansion of segmental duplications, and bursts of retroviral integrations [45], cell-cycle alterations being derived in human compared to chimpanzee and orangutan pluripotent stem cells [46], Alu diversity in chimpanzees being 1.7 times higher than in humans, consistent with lower genetic diversity overall in humans [47], and chimpanzees having higher levels of line 1 mobility than humans, consistent with their inherently higher tolerance for genetic diversity

relative to humans [48]. Overall, even without intentional efforts to look for evidence for the pongid clade, there are already overwhelming data from both molecular studies and trait analyses supporting these groupings.

It is reassuring to finally see a unity of genes and traits in the hominid phylogeny, which has long been one of the most striking cases of disconnect between genes and traits. We fully anticipate more evidence supporting the pongid clade to emerge in future studies. The validation of the molecular phylogeny constructed using methods based on the maximum genetic diversity theory additionally strengthens the evidence for the theory.

Methods:

Whole-genome assembly-assembly alignment plots revealing synteny data were captured as screen shots from the CGV website. We visually inspected the degree of synteny for each pair of species within the apes. A higher degree of synteny is inferred when there are fewer reverse alignments, when a chromosome is not aligned to multiple chromosomes, or when there are more forward alignments. For any comparisons AB vs. BC, the chromosomes that support a higher degree of synteny for AB or BC were identified and recorded. In comparisons AB vs. BC that involves a shared species B, the chromosome name being recorded refers to that of B. In comparisons involving both great apes and humans, the chromosome name being recorded refers to that of the great apes, except when B is human in an AB vs. BC comparison. For comparisons between humans and gibbons, the chromosome name recorded refers to that of humans.

We defined a synteny ratio in an AB vs. BC or AB vs. CD comparison as BC/AB or CD/AB , i.e., the number of chromosomes with higher synteny for BC or CD divided by the number of chromosomes with higher synteny for AB. A smaller ratio (<1) indicates greater degree of synteny for AB relative to BC or CD.

Acknowledgements:

We thank the CGV team at NCBI for performing the whole-genome assembly-assembly alignments and making the results publicly accessible. SH was not supported for this work by any funding agencies. We thank Professors Madelaine Bohme and Martin Pickford for their critical readings of the manuscript.

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Tables:

Table 1. Synteny analysis of hominoids. For any pair comparisons AB vs. BC or CD, the chromosomes (denoted by their numerical names) that support a higher degree of synteny for AB or BC/CD are listed, with a chromosome name followed by a negative sign indicating support for BC/CD. The summary column lists the number of synteny supporting AB vs BC/CD. In comparisons AB vs. BC that involves a shared species B, the chromosome name listed refers to that of B. In comparisons involving both great apes and humans, the chromosome name listed refers to that of the great apes, except when B is human in an AB vs. BC comparison. For comparisons between humans and gibbons, the chromosome name refers to that of humans.

Pairs	Summary	Informative chromosomes
CC vs. CG	20 vs 3	1, 2-, 3, 4, 5-, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13-, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, x, y
OO vs. GO	20 vs 2	1, 2-, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11-, 12, 13, 15, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, x, y
CG vs. CO	10 vs 5	2, 3, 4, 5-, 6, 7-, 9, 10, 11, 13-, 15-, 16, 19-, x
CG vs. GO	9 vs 4	2, 3-, 5-, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 13-, 16, 20, 22-, x
CG vs. CH	8 vs 6	1, 3, 4-, 5-, 7-, 8-, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15-, 17, 19-
CG vs. HO	11 vs 5	1, 2, 4-, 5-, 6, 7-, 9, 11, 12, 13, 15-, 16, 17, 19-, 23, x
CH vs. CO	6 vs 6	1-, 2, 6, 8, 9, 11-, 12-, 13-, 14-, 17-, 19, x
CH vs. GO	10 vs 9	1-, 2, 3-, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11-, 12-, 13-, 14-, 15, 17-, 19, 20, 21-, 22-, x
CH vs. HO	8 vs 6	3, 4-, 5-, 7, 9-, 10, 11, 12-, 14-, 16, 19, 20, 21-, x
CG vs. HG	6 vs 1	1, 6, 10, 11, 12, 17, 22-
HG vs. GO	5 vs 8	1-, 2, 3-, 5-, 6, 9, 11-, 12-, 13-, 17-, 20, 21-, x
HG vs. HO	5 vs 6	3, 5-, 6-, 7, 8-, 11, 12-, 14-, 17-, 19, x
CO vs. HO	6 vs 2	1, 4-, 10-, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17
GO vs. HO	8 vs 5	1, 3, 4-, 6, 7-, 10-, 11, 12, 13, 15-, 17, 19-, 22
HO vs. Hgi	17 vs 1	4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, x, y

Figure legends:

Figure 1. Phylogenetic tree of hominoids. A. The tree based on anatomy or the slow clock method. B. The popular molecular tree based on the molecular clock and fast evolving sequences.

Figure 2. Plots of whole-genome assembly-assembly alignments among hominoids. Both forward alignments (green) and reverse alignments (purple) are shown. A. *Pan paniscus* vs. *Pan troglodytes* or chimpanzee vs. chimpanzee (CC). B. *Pongo pygmaeus* vs. *Pongo abelii* or orangutan vs. orangutan (OO). C. *Gorilla gorilla gorilla* vs. *Pan troglodytes* or gorilla vs. chimpanzee (CG). D. *Pongo abelii* vs. *Pan troglodytes* (CO). E. *Pongo abelii* vs. *Gorilla gorilla gorilla* (GO). F. *Pan troglodytes* vs. *Homo sapiens* (CH). G. *Gorilla gorilla gorilla* vs. *Homo sapiens* (GH). H. *Pongo abelii* vs. *Homo sapiens* (OH). I. *Nomascus leucogenys* vs. *Homo sapiens* or gibbon vs. human (HGi).

Figure 3. Synteny among hominoids. For any comparison listed (e.g., CC vs. CG), the synteny ratios shown represent the number of chromosomes with a higher degree of synteny for the latter (CG) compared to the former (CC). C: chimpanzees, G: gorillas, O: orangutans, H: humans, Gi: gibbons.

A.

Pan paniscus NHGRI_mPanPan1-v2.0_pri ([GCF_029289425.2](#))

B.

Pongo pygmaeus NHGRI_mPonPyg2-v2.0_pri ([GCF_02885625.2](#))

C.

Gorilla gorilla gorilla NHGRI_mGorGor1-v2.0_pri ([GCF_029281585.2](#))

D.

Pongo abelii NHGRI_mPonAbe1-v2.0_pri ([GCF_028885655.2](#))

E.

Pongo abelii NHGRI_mPonAbe1-v2.0_pri ([GCF_028885655.2](#))

F.

Pan troglodytes NHGRI_mPanTro3-v2.0_pri ([GCF_028858775.2](#))

Download data

Download image

G.

Gorilla gorilla gorilla NHGRI_mGorGor1-v2.0_pri ([GCF_029281585.2](#))

Homo sapiens T2T-CHM13v2.0 ([GCF_009914755.1](#))

H.

Pongo abelii NHGRI_mPonAbe1-v2.0_pri ([GCF_028885655.2](#))

Homo sapiens T2T-CHM13v2.0 ([GCF_009914755.1](#))

I.

Nomascus leucogenys Asia_NLE_v1 ([GCF_006542625.1](#))

Homo sapiens T2T-CHM13v2.0 ([GCF_009914755.1](#))

